

Digital Democracy Preference Toolkit

Authors

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Abstract

The toolkit examines the practical expectations of European citizens and government actors regarding Digital Democracy Applications (DDAs). Using a mixed-methods design, the research identifies aligned and conflicting interests among these stakeholders. The resulting report provides a clear understanding of DDA requirements and a set of recommendations for developing a DDA that meets aspirations for relevance, user-friendliness, and security from both back-end and front-end perspectives.

Benefits

- A list of recommendations for DDA development, informed by ± 400 European citizens and 70 government actors.
- An overview of DDA implementation challenges and coping strategies drawn from practical experience"
- A mapping of conflicts and synergies between citizens' and public actors' expectations, needs, and concerns regarding digital solutions and their features.
- A bridging of the gap between the technical availability of digital tools for citizen participation and stakeholders' actual aspirations, highlighting a need for hybrid, easily adaptable solutions that allow a human touch.

Why is it important?

Technical availability or ingenuity alone do not guarantee uptake by the public or public organisers. For DDAs to have a genuine chance of success and to provide a robust foundation for digital participation processes, they should ideally meet the expectations, needs and concerns of the various stakeholders who will use them. Otherwise, newly designed solutions risk becoming obsolete before launch. Furthermore, to avoid bias in both participation and its final results, it is essential to put in place sufficient supporting measures so that all stakeholders can (learn to) contribute meaningfully.

Online resource

The Digital Democracy Preference Toolkit is available for free online:
<https://zenodo.org/records/18258934>

Quote

There is no silver bullet approach to DDA development, as various options are possible and preferences prove context dependent. With the recommendations presented in this report, however, we hope that those already working on digital citizen participation can further grow their ambitions and that those not yet doing so find inspiration to overcome their reservations.

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Involved

Stakeholders

Citizens & citizen-facing CSOs

Policymakers & policy-facing CSOs, Public Administration

Software Developers & companies

Researchers

